

Highly selective catalytic-spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) by using calmagite-bromate redox reaction

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A highly selective and sensitive kinetic method for the determination of trace amounts of vanadium(V) is reported. The method is based on catalytic effect of bromate on the oxidation of calmagite in acidic solutions. The reaction is followed spectrophotometrically by measuring the change in absorbance of calmagite at $\lambda = 523$ nm using a fixed time method (5 min). Under optimum conditions vanadium can be determined in the range of 2–10 ng ml⁻¹. The detection limit based on 3S_b criterion was 0.27 ng ml⁻¹, and relative standard deviation for ten replicate measurements of 5 ng ml⁻¹ of V^V was 1.2%. Influence of 29 foreign ions were observed. The method was applied for the determination of vanadium in soil samples.

Vanadium is a pollutant and its determination at trace level is of increasing importance in biological and environmental samples. The toxicity of vanadium is dependant on its oxidation state with vanadium(V) being more toxic than other oxidation state¹. Vanadium has wide application in catalyst industry, electronic equipment and ceramics. Therefore its determination in minerals and industrial samples is of great importance.

Instrumental techniques such as atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS)², inductively coupled plasma emission spectrometry (ICP-ES)^{3,4}, neutron activation analysis (NAA)⁵, ICP-MS⁶, flow injection analysis (FIA)⁷ and catalytic methods⁸ are currently used for the determination of vanadium.

Kinetic-catalytic methods have been recognized as offering a valuable approach to trace analysis. Many kinetic-catalytic methods have been proposed for the determination of vanadium^{9–14}.

In present work a simple and highly selective catalytic-spectrophotometric method for vanadium(V) have been studied. The method is based on the catalytic effect of vanadium(V) on calmagite-bromate redox reaction.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of calmagite in sulfuric acid solution shows that maximum absorbance occurs at 523 nm. This reagent undergoes an oxidation reaction with bromate in acidic media in presence of vanadium(V) as catalyst and its absorbance is decreased with time. The catalytic effect was monitored spectrophotometrically by measuring the decrease in absorbance (ΔA) at a fixed time method (5 min).

Effect of variables :

The effect of the concentration of each reagent on the rate of reaction was studied in order to optimize the variable.

The optimum concentration of calmagite was established. There was no change in absorbance when calmagite concentration was above 1.4×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ in the final solution (Fig. 1) so it was chosen as the optimum value.

Fig. 1. Effect of calmagite concentration of the change in absorbance.

The influence of bromate concentration on the reaction was studied. The results showed that by increasing the bromate concentration, the rate of reaction was increased but at higher bromate concentration than 2×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ the uncatalyzed reaction proceeded very fast and the solu-

tion becomes colorless rapidly, therefore a concentration of $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ was chosen for studies.

The effect of acidity on the reaction was studied and it was found that the reaction does not proceed in neutral or alkaline solutions and it only occurs in acidic media. Therefore the concentration of sulfuric acid was optimized. The highest change in absorbance occurred when acid concentration was in the range of 4.4×10^{-2} – $8.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in the final solution. Thus $4.4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ was chosen as the most suitable (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Effect of sulfuric acid concentration on the reaction.

Increasing the temperature increased the analytical sensitivity of the catalyzed reaction, and 30 ± 0.1 was chosen for convenience. The effect of ionic strength on the reaction rate was studied by the addition of KNO_3 and it was found that there was no significant change in ΔA up to the ionic strength of 0.2 mol dm^{-3} .

Analytical characteristics :

Calibration graph was obtained by applying the fixed time method and using the recommended procedure. The calibration graph of change in absorbance (ΔA) versus vanadium(V) concentration was linear in the range of 2–10 ng ml^{-1} ($t = 5 \text{ min}$). The equation of the line was $\Delta A = 0.069 + 0.035 C_M$, where C_M is vanadium concentration in ng ml^{-1} and the correlation coefficient was 0.9994. The detection limit based on $3S_b$ criterion was 0.27 ng ml^{-1} and the relative standard deviation (RSD) for ten replicate measurements of 5 ng ml^{-1} vanadium(V) was 1.2%.

Interference study :

Interference effects of various cations and anions on

vanadium-catalyzed reaction were studied for 5 ng ml^{-1} of vanadium(V). A relative error of 3% was considered tolerable. The tolerance ratio for the ions studied are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of foreign ions on the determination of 5 ng ml^{-1} of vanadium(V)

Ions	$C_{\text{ion}} / C_{\text{vanadium}}$
$\text{K}^+, \text{Na}^+, \text{Ca}^{2+}$	10000
$\text{MoO}_4^{2-}, \text{S}^{2-}$	5000
$\text{Hg}^{2+}, \text{Cu}^{2+}, \text{Cd}^{2+}, \text{Mn}^{2+},$ $\text{Pb}^{2+}, \text{Ag}^+, \text{V}^{3+}, \text{HCO}_3^-,$ $\text{CO}_3^{2-}, \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-, \text{NO}_3^-,$ $\text{NO}_2^-, \text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$	1000
$\text{SCN}^-, \text{F}^-, \text{PO}_4^{3-}, \text{H}_2\text{PO}_4^-,$ $\text{SO}_4^{2-}, \text{IO}_3^-, \text{I}^-, \text{SO}_3^{2-}$	500
$\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$	100
$\text{Fe}^{2+}, \text{Fe}^{3+}$	50

Determination of V^V in ore samples :

In order to test the reliability of the method, it was applied to the determination of vanadium(V) in soil samples. 1.0 g of the sample, 6.0 g of sodium carbonate and 0.2 g sodium nitrate was transferred in a platinum crucible and mixed well. Then it was placed in an electrical furnace (1000°) for 40 min. The flux was dissolved in hot water and diluted to 100 ml. The solution was treated under the recommended procedure. The results obtained were compared with those obtained by the extraction-spectrophotometric method, used for analysis of vanadium in soil samples¹⁵. The results in Table 2 show agreements between the two methods.

Table 2. Determination of vanadium(V) in soil samples

Sample no.	Amount of vanadium(V) $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$	
	Kinetic method	Conventional method
1	370 ± 3	390 ± 5
2	41 ± 1	39 ± 2
3	380 ± 3	358 ± 5

* Each number is average of five measurements.

Conclusion :

The proposed method was found to be highly selective and sensitive for the determination of low levels of vanadium(V) ($2\text{--}10 \text{ ng ml}^{-1}$). The method was more tolerant to interferences than many previously reported methods¹¹. The results shows that the selectivity achieved by proposed

method is high since only Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} interfere when present at higher ratios than 50, which could easily be removed using a cation exchange resin. Due to its reactivity. The method was applied for the determination of vanadium in soil samples directly. Preconcentration such as extraction¹⁴ technique is not required.

Experimental

Reagents : Analytical grade reagents and distilled-deionized water were used throughout the experiment. $1000 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ vanadium(V) standard stock solution was prepared by dissolving 1.148 g ammonium metavanadate (Merck) in water and diluted to 500 ml in volumetric flask. Further dilutions were made daily. $5.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ calmagite (Merck) solution and 0.1 M sodium bromate (Merck) were prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of each reagent in water. 0.44 mol dm^{-3} sulfuric acid was prepared by diluting 25 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid ($d = 1.84$, 95–97%, Merck) to one liter.

Apparatus : Absorption spectra were recorded using a Jasco Model 7850 UV-Visible spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells and absorption measurements were made using a Perkin-Elmer 5508 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. A Gallen Kamp BJH-400-010D thermostat in which the temperature could be fixed within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ was used.

Procedure : Into a 10 ml volumetric flask, 1 ml of $5.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ calmagite solution, 1 ml of 0.44 mol dm^{-3} sulfuric acid and 1 ml of a vanadate standard solution were added so that the final vanadium(V) concentration was in the range of 2–10 ng ml^{-1} . Enough water was added to make solution to ca. 8 ml, then 2 ml of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} bromate was added and the solution was diluted to 10 ml. The

absorbance was measured against water after 5 min. The zero time was taken as the moment at which the last drop of bromate had been added. All the solutions were kept in a thermostat bath ($30 \pm 0.1^\circ$) before use.

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